

a quantitative method for determining the apparent activation energy consistent with a given function $f(\alpha)$.

$$b=0; B_0 = \log \alpha - \log p(x)$$

$$b=1; B_1 = \log \left(\ln \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \right) - \log p(x)$$

$$b=2; B_2 = \log \left(\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \right) - \log p(x)$$

and the value of $g(\alpha)$ are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	Temp. °C	W mg	$\log \alpha$	$\log \left(\frac{1}{1-\alpha} \right)$	$\log \left(\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \right)$
1.	190	4.50	-1.634	-1.629	-1.624
2.	200	4.45	-1.332	-1.322	-1.311
3.	210	4.30	-0.934	-0.907	-0.880
4.	220	4.05	-0.633	-0.577	-0.518
5.	230	3.75	-0.429	-0.332	-0.227
6.	240	3.20	-0.202	-0.004	0.227
7.	250	2.65	-0.053	0.332	0.880
8.	260	2.50	-0.020	0.486	1.310

$$W_0 = 4.55 \text{ mg}, W_t = 2.440 \text{ mg.}$$

For quantitative evaluation of the value of E_a , the arithmetical mean of B_0 , B_1 and B_2 have been calculated and also the standard deviation δ for all the three pre-supposed order of reactions. The δ is obtained from the relation,

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{(B_i - \bar{B})^2}{r}}$$

where B_i is any value, \bar{B} their arithmetical mean and r the number of values. The various values for the corresponding B_0 , B_1 and B_2 are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2

B_0		B_1		B_2	
E_a	δ_0	E_a	δ_1	E_a	δ_2
24	0.102 8	32	0.057 3	42	0.147 2
26	0.099 1	34	0.043 3	44	0.135 8
28	0.112 0	36	0.069 7	46	0.136 1

It is apparent from Table 2 that the standard deviations are minimum if the first order reaction is accepted, and the value for δ is minimum for $E_a = 34.0 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ and corresponds to 0.0433. The value of the arithmetical mean, i.e. \bar{B} corresponds to 17.554.

The frequency factor Z for the solid state kinetics is evaluated as $\log Z = 17.319$ by means of the relation,

$$\log Z = \bar{B} + \log Rq - \log E_a$$

where q is the heating rate and R the gas constant.

The apparent activation entropy, ΔS^\ddagger is calculated as +9.88 e.u. from relation,

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = 2.303 \log (Zh/kT)$$

The value for T in this equation is the temperature $T_{1/2}$ at which the weight-loss is half the total loss during the step of transformation under consideration.

The values for E_a with order of reaction $b=1$ by Freeman and Carroll and Zsako are 35.69 and 34.00 kcal mol^{-1} respectively. The values for E_a , b calculated by the procedures mentioned earlier seem to be in good agreement with each other and thus may be utilised in the study of solid state reaction mechanism.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (A.P.S.).

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Kinetic Analysis of Consecutive First Order Reaction: Oxidation of Succinic Acid Dihydrazide by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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Manuscript received 12 May 1989, accepted 19 June 1990

A number of oxidants have been employed in the kinetic studies of the oxidation of hydrazides¹. But no attempts have been made so far to study the kinetics of oxidation of aliphatic dihydrazides by alkaline hexacyanoferrate. Here, we report the kinetic analysis of the oxidation of succinic acid dihydrazide by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III).

Experimental

Succinic acid dihydrazide, prepared by known method² was crystallised from ethanol and used as such. Potassium hexacyanoferrate and other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used. All the kinetic runs were carried out in a thermostated ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) water-bath. Reaction rates were determined by estimating remaining amount of hexacyanoferrate(III) spectrophotometrically using a DDR Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer at 420 nm. The absorption due to

TABLE 1 - RATE DATA FOR OXIDATION OF SUCCINIC ACID HYDRAZIDE BY HEXACYANOFERRATE(III) AT 35°

[A] × 10 ⁴ M	[k ₂ Fe(CN) ₆] × 10 ³ M	[NaOH] × 10 ⁴ M	k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹ 35% R/(70% R)	k ₂ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹ 35% R/(70% R)
1.0	1.0	1.0	3.074	6.135 (6.382)	3.067 (3.197)
2.0	1.0	1.0	3.390	6.765 (7.039)	3.382 (3.519)
3.0	1.0	1.0	3.978	7.739 (8.052)	3.869 (4.026)
4.0	1.0	1.0	4.358	8.697 (9.049)	4.348 (4.524)
5.0	1.0	1.0	5.056	10.09 (10.41)	5.045 (5.249)
2.0	0.85	1.0	3.276	6.538 (6.802)	3.269 (3.401)
2.0	0.90	1.0	3.280	6.546 (6.810)	3.273 (3.405)
2.0	0.95	1.0	3.381	6.747 (7.020)	3.373 (3.510)
2.0	1.00	1.0	3.390	6.765 (7.039)	3.382 (3.519)
2.0	1.05	1.0	3.210	6.407 (6.666)	3.203 (3.333)
2.0	1.0	0.65	3.190	6.366 (6.623)	3.183 (3.311)
2.0	1.0	0.80	3.295	6.576 (6.841)	3.288 (3.420)
2.0	1.0	1.00	3.390	6.765 (7.039)	3.382 (3.519)
2.0	1.0	1.4	3.329	6.644 (6.912)	3.322 (3.456)
2.0	1.0	1.8	3.843	7.669 (7.979)	3.834 (3.989)

hexacyanoferrate(II) formed is negligible². Pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{total}) were computed by least-squares method.

Results and Discussion

The rate constants k_1 and k_2 of first and second step of the reaction were determined by Swain's time-ratio method⁴ and listed in Table 1 along with k_{total} observed experimentally. The values of k_1 and k_2 for standard run for 35% reaction were 6.765×10^{-3} and $3.382 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ respectively, and the value of k_2 is nearly equal to k_{total} ($3.390 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) observed experimentally. This shows that second step of the reaction is slow and rate determining.

Concentrations of succinic acid dihydrazide, enolate of dihydrazide and succinic acid

Fig. 1. Plots of concentration against time of (A) succinic acid dihydrazide, (B) enolate of dihydrazide and (C) succinic acid monohydrazide.

NOTES

Scheme 1

The final rate expression is given as $-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}}{dt} = 3k_1k_2[\text{A}][\bar{\text{O}}\text{H}][\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$

monohydrazide (designated as A, B and C respectively) were calculated by Esson's method⁵. The values are plotted against time (Fig. 1) to indicate the consecutive nature of the reaction, which can also be confirmed by applying standard method. Powell⁶ showed that for a simple as well as complex reaction, a plot of percentage reaction

against $\log t$ produces a curve, the form of which essentially depends upon the type of reaction and possibly on some dimensionless parameters. The plot of percentage reaction (50δ , where $\delta = \beta + 2\gamma$) against $\log \tau$ gives a curve and that against $\log t$ exhibits identical curve but shifting horizontally by an amount $-\log k_1$. For succinic acid

dihydrazide the curve is shifted by 2.17 for 40% reaction. The shift corresponds to $k_1 = 6.76 \times 10^{-8} \text{ min}^{-1}$ which has been found to be similar to that of $k_1 (6.765 \times 10^{-8} \text{ min}^{-1})$ obtained by Swain's time-ratio method. This technique besides determining rate constant, indicates that the reaction studied is consecutive reaction.

The reaction between succinic acid dihydrazide and hexacyanoferrate(III) was investigated in the temperature range 30–50°. The values of energy of activation, enthalpy of activation, entropy of activation and frequency factor were found to be 39.97 kJ mol⁻¹, 37.38 kJ mol⁻¹, -40.89 e.u. and $2.1 \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$ respectively.

The variation of concentration of potassium sulphate showed a positive salt-effect indicating that the reaction may involve the species of the same charge or a charged species and neutral molecule and which should correspond to a negative entropy change⁷.

Different sets of the reaction mixtures containing known excess of hexacyanoferrate(III) over succinic acid dihydrazide were kept at 35° in presence of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ NaOH}$ for 48 h. The amounts of hexacyanoferrate left in all the cases were consistent with the stoichiometric equation. It is observed that one mole of substrate required four moles of oxidant. The malonic acid, nitrogen and the hydrogen are the main products of the reaction. The acid was detected by tlc while the nitrogen by Dumas method.

At constant OH⁻ the plot of $(-\frac{dc}{dt})^{-1}$ against 1/[sub-

strate] gave a straight line satisfying Michaelis-Menten type⁸ reciprocal relationship and indicating the probability of the complex formation between oxidant and substrate prior to the rate-determining step.

It was observed that the rate increases significantly with an increase in alkali concentration. Alkali dependence of oxidation process clearly indicates that the oxidation of dihydrazide takes place through an intermediate anion of the substrate formed by reaction with hydroxyl ion⁹.

Mechanism: A scheme for the oxidation of succinic acid dihydrazide by alkaline hexacyanoferrate has been proposed (Scheme 1).

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Photoirradiation of some 3-Benzyloxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyrans

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Manuscript received 18 July 1989, revised 15 March 1990, accepted 3 July 1990

FLAVONE (2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran) is known to photosensitise the *cis-trans* isomerisation of stilbene¹. Since various derivatives of flavone occur in plants and are exposed to light, their acting as photodynamic-transferring agents is not remote². Our interest in the photochemistry of flavones³ and related compounds prompted us to study the effect of light on 3-benzyloxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyrans (1–3).

- 1, 4, 5; R=F
 2, 6, 7; R=Cl
 3, 8; R=H

Scheme 1